

A Machine-Learning-Based Green View Index incorporating Vegetation Type and measuring its association with Street-level Land Surface Temperature in London

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Summary

Urban greenery plays a crucial role in mitigating adverse effects and enhancing well-being. However, traditional assessment of urban greenery such as NVDI and GVI treats greenery homogenously and often does not consider the vegetation type, species and composition of greenery. This study proposed new GVI, applying machine learning methods on street imagery, that better captures the heterogeneity of vegetation type and position in the scene. We then examined its efficacy by correlating with street land surface temperature. The results contribute to the exploration of quantifying urban greenery, and insights for the better planning and management of urban greenery in London.

KEYWORDS: Google Street Views, Urban Greenery, Land Surface Temperature, GeoAI

1.0 Background

Urban environments are essential for human beings, but increased urbanisation poses challenges like the Urban Heat Island effect as well as health issues caused by high temperature [1]. Many cities aim to improve urban greenery in both tackling climate challenges and improving quality of life. For example, Greater London proposed initiatives to enhance its green infrastructure and natural environment in London Plan 2021 [2]. Urban greenery includes all trees, shrubs, grasses, and other green vegetation in urban regions [3]. They provide many benefits to urban environment like absorbing air pollution [4], mitigating the effects of urban heat islands [5], and enhancing physical activities and promoting citizens' well-being. To maximize the benefits of urban greenery, it's important to have a detailed understanding of its distribution and quantity in cities.

However, traditional assessment of urban greenery using remote sensing methods like the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and greenery canopy cover, misses both the vertical dimension of urban greenery, species and types of greenery. The Green View Index (GVI) had been proposed in recent years to better reflect eye-level urban greenery [6]. However, these indices treat urban greenery homogenously and does not consider vegetation type, species, geometry and composition. In reality, each type of plants provide different benefits [7,8] and how greenery is composed in the street can change its perception. For example, a smaller plant positioned more proximate to pedestrian can have greater visual prominence than a larger plant further away [9]. Therefore, we proposed a novel ML-based GVI that better captures the heterogeneity of greenery type and its eye-level position. We then associate the new indices with street land surface temperature (SLST). The results provide additional insights for urban greenery management and planning.

2.0 Datasets

This study focuses on Inner London at the Lower Layer Super Output Area (LSOA) level which contains 1736 LSOAs. We sample five random street midpoints at each LSOA totaling 8,558 points and gather four 640*640 street view images (SVI) using the Google Street View API (shown in figure

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1&2). After removing invalid images, 30,062 SVIs were processed. This study then collected mean land surface temperature data from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS Collection 2 Tier 1 Level-2, made available on Google Earth Engine, between the period from May to September 2022. Additionally, population density data was obtained from the Office for National Statistics (2023) which is used as a control variable in the regression analysis.

Figure 1. All sampling points in Inner London.

Figure 2. Example of four street views from four direction in one sample point.

3.0 Methodology

This study presents a framework to calculate new GVIs, and explore the relationship between SLST and green metrics at LSOA level. The pipeline includes four parts: (a) data collection, (b) variables calculation, (c) regression modelling, and (d) mapping and analysis.

Figure 3. The pipeline of study.

3.1 Pixel-level greenery type segmentation

This research uses a Transformer-based SegFormer [10] pretrained on ADE20k[≡] to segment GSV at the pixel-level into 150 semantic classes, such as buildings, trees and pavements. The Segformer architecture is characterized by its hierarchical Transformer encoder and a lightweight multilayer perception decoder [10]. The model was selected as it showed strong performance when compared to architecture such as DeepLab V3+ on the ADE20K dataset [10].

[≡] Assessed from Hugging Face (2023)

Figure 4. Architecture overview of SegFormer [10].

3.2 Monocular image depth estimation

In this research, we also estimated the relative depth of the scene through monocular depth estimation. In particular, we adopted the MiDaSv3 architecture that has been pretrained on multiple datasets [11]. The ResNet-based architecture was first introduced by Ranftl et al. [12], which includes a depth encoder, a shared-parameter depth decoder, an adaptive oversampling module, and a Multi-Scale Feature Modulation [13]. MiDaS, trained on diverse datasets with millions of samples, is recognized as a robust monocular depth estimation model [14, 15].

Figure 5. Architecture overview of MiDaSv3 [13].

3.2 Green View Index

The original GVI or OGVI will act as a baseline for the study which measures the percentage of total green area four images at each sampling point [16]. Two new GVIs was proposed where weights are assigned according to vegetation types and distance from the viewpoint. The first proposed measure is Constant GVI (CGVI), based on a knowledge-based approach, where trees are the most preferred in urban landscapes due to cooling/shade/air improvement/aesthetics, followed by shrubs for aesthetic benefits and then grass. This study manually assigned a weight of 0.55 for trees, 0.25 for shrubs, and 0.2 for grass. The second proposed measure is Depth GVI (DGVI) which utilises normalized relative average depth for each type of vegetation as additional weights. Closer plants have a higher depth, so they were assigned more weights. The calculation formula are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. GVIs calculations.

GVIs	Formula
OGVI	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 Area_{tree_i} + Area_{shrub_i} + Area_{grass_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^4 Area_{total_i}} \times 100\%$
CGVI	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 Area_{tree_i} \times W_{tree} + Area_{shrub_i} \times W_{shrub} + Area_{grass_i} \times W_{grass}}{\sum_{i=1}^4 Area_{total_i}} \times 100\%$
DGVI	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^{k1} \sum_{m=1}^{k2} \sum_{n=1}^{k3} Area_{tree_ij} \times W_{tree_ij} + Area_{shrub_im} \times W_{shrub_im} + Area_{grass_in} \times W_{grass_in}}{\sum_{i=1}^4 Area_{total_i}} \times 100\%$

**Explanation:* i is the four directions (east, south, west, and north) of GSV; j is the number of trees; m is the number of shrub objects; n is the number of grass object; Area_{tree} is the number of tree pixels, W_{tree} is the weights of tree; Area_{shrub} is the number of shrub pixels, W_{shrub} is the weights of shrub; Area_{grass} is the number of grass pixels, W_{grass} is the weights of grass; and Area_{total} is the total pixel number.

3.3 SLST calculations

Moreover, we then measured land surface temperature for the same street. More precisely, we calculate the mean SLST values within a 20-meter radius of each street [16, 17]. This approach ensures that the average temperature within a 20-meter buffer more accurately represents the street temperature.

3.4 Regression analysis

The correlations between SLST and various features in 1,736 LSOAs are explored, using 6 regression models based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to assess the impact of GVIs on SLST.

4.0 Results and discussion

4.1 Qualitative results

Trees, shrubs, and grass were segmented for 30,062 GSV using SegFormer and qualitatively assessed. The percentage of tree pixels is 35.13, shrub pixels is 0.31, and grass pixels is 6.63 (Figure 6).. According to the segmentation of each object, the average depth were able to calculate. The proportion for Tree 1 and Tree 2 are 33.01 and 2.12, with average depths of 16.22 and 2.65, respectively (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Example of image segmentation.

Figure 7. Example of detailed component segmentation and depth estimation for tree.

4.2 New GVIs index and Street Land Surface Temperature

The spatial distribution of all the variables are shown in Figure 8. The two new proposed GVIs have a similar trend to OGVI, with the lowest values in central Inner London and the highest in the southern and southeastern parts. Inner London mostly experiences higher summer street temperatures around 40 °C, with some cooler areas in the central, southern, and southeastern parts. And lastly, the population density is higher in the north sometimes exceeding 20,000 people/km.

Figure 8. Spatial distribution of all variables.

4.3 Regression analysis

Six experiments were conducted using OLS and GWR to examine associations between SLST and different GVIs controlling for population density. Their detail results are shown in Table 1 and 2. In general, OGVI and CGVI performed similarly when predicting SLST while DGVI performed the worst. OGVI performed best for the OLS model while considering spatial autocorrelation, CGVI performed slightly better than OGVI for the GWR model, with an R2 of 0.187.

Table 2. Summary of results and diagnosis from the OLS analysis.

Model	Variables	Intercept	Coefficient	P-value	VIF	R2	AICc	F-Statistic (P-value)	Moran's I on Residual (P-value)
M 1	OGVI		-0.3352	<0.001	1.027	0.113	4725.379	110.407 (0.001)	0.623 (0.001)
	POPDENS	1.96E-15	0.0060	0.794					
M 2	CGVI		-0.3292	<0.001	1.014	0.111	4730.256	107.667 (0.001)	0.626 (0.001)
	POPDENS	1.91196E-15	0.0214	0.348					
M 3	DGVI		-0.2685	<0.001	1.025	0.074	4800.061	69.273 (0.001)	0.627 (0.001)
	POPDENS	1.95156E-15	0.0187	0.424					

Table 3. Summary of results and diagnosis from the GWR analysis.

Model	Variables	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	3rd Qu.	Max.	R2	AICc	Bandwidth
M 4	Intercept	-0.162	-0.098	-0.059	0.036	0.173	0.182	4593.126	1529.798
	OGVI	-0.429	-0.349	-0.286	-0.224	-0.144			
	POPDENS	-0.044	-0.032	-0.022	0.007	0.047			
M 5	Intercept	0.179	-0.098	-0.053	0.044	0.187	0.187	4584.505	1505.409
	CGVI	-0.431	-0.352	-0.282	-0.218	-0.134			
	POPDENS	-0.036	-0.024	-0.010	0.013	0.056			
M 6	Intercept	-0.158	-0.104	-0.066	0.034	0.189	0.149	4663.398	1466.616
	DWGI	-0.371	-0.274	-0.213	-0.161	-0.077			
	POPDENS	-0.031	-0.020	-0.009	0.019	0.072			

5.0 Conclusions

This study evaluated the urban greenery in Inner London by proposing 2 new GVIs, and explored their effectiveness in predicting street land surface temperature. The new GVI measures, namely CGVI and DGVI, were designed to capture additional information about vegetation type and depth in urban greenery. However, the additional vegetation information doesn't seem to add significant explanatory power when regressing with LST in an OLS, and only marginally so with a GWR. There are two potential reasons: i) Missing covariate such as building height; ii) Low resolution of LST measurements (e.g. LandSat Thermal). Although segmenting by type (e.g. tree, shrub, grass) does not substantially improve land surface temperature predictions, the research contributes to a more nuanced exploration of urban greenery that offer valuable insights to improved planning and management of green spaces in London.

References

- [1] O' Brien, D. T., Gridley, B., Trlica, A., Wang, J. A., & Shrivastava, A. (2020). Urban heat islets: Street segments, land surface temperatures, and medical emergencies during heat advisories. *American Journal of Public Health*, 110(7), 994-1001.
- [2] Greater London Authority. (2021). The London Plan. Available at https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/the_london_plan_2021.pdf
- [3] Bentsen, P., Lindholst, A. C., & Konijnendijk, C. C. (2010). Reviewing eight years of Urban Forestry & Urban Greening: Taking stock, looking ahead. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 9(4), 273-280.
- [4] Liu, H. L., & Shen, Y. S. (2014). The impact of green space changes on air pollution and microclimates: A case study of the Taipei metropolitan area. *Sustainability*, 6(12), 8827-8855.
- [5] Sun, R., & Chen, L. (2017). Effects of green space dynamics on urban heat islands: Mitigation and diversification. *Ecosystem Services*, 23, 38-46.
- [6] Li, X., & Ratti, C. (2018). Mapping the spatial distribution of shade provision of street trees in Boston using Google Street View panoramas. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 31, 109-119.
- [7] Bao, Y., Gao, M., Luo, D., & Zhou, X. (2022). The influence of plant community characteristics in urban parks on the microclimate. *Forests*, 13(9), 1342.
- [8] Liao, J., Tan, X., & Li, J. (2021). Evaluating the vertical cooling performances of urban vegetation scenarios in a residential environment. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 39, 102313.
- [9] Bringslimark, T., Hartig, T., & Patil, G. G. (2009). The psychological benefits of indoor plants: A critical review of the experimental literature. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 29(4), 422-433.
- [10] Xie, E., Wang, W., Yu, Z., Anandkumar, A., Alvarez, J. M., & Luo, P. (2021). SegFormer: Simple and efficient design for semantic segmentation with transformers. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34, 12077-12090.
- [11] PyTorch Hub. (2023). MiDaS v3.0 model. https://pytorch.org/hub/intelisl_midass_v2/
- [12] Ranftl, R., Lasinger, K., Hafner, D., Schindler, K., & Koltun, V. (2020). Towards robust

- monocular depth estimation: Mixing datasets for zero-shot cross-dataset transfer. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 44(3), 1623-1637.
- [13] Ranftl, R., Bochkovskiy, A., & Koltun, V. (2021). Vision transformers for dense prediction. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision* (pp. 12179-12188).
- [14] Romero-Lugo, A., Magadan-Salazar, A., Fuentes-Pacheco, J., & Pinto-Elías, R. (2022). A Comparison of Deep Neural Networks for Monocular Depth Map Estimation in Natural Environments Flying at Low Altitude. *Sensors*, 22(24), 9830.
- [15] Ehret, T. (2023). Monocular Depth Estimation: a Review of the 2022 State of the Art. *Image Processing On Line*, 13, 38-56.
- [16] Li, X., & Ratti, C. (2018). Mapping the spatial distribution of shade provision of street trees in Boston using Google Street View panoramas. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 31, 109-119.
- [17] Yu, X., Zhao, G., Chang, C., Yuan, X., & Heng, F. (2018). Bgvi: A new index to estimate street-side greenery using baidu street view image. *Forests*, 10(1), 3.

Biographies

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